

TEACHING PRODUCTIVE LANGUAGE SKILLS THROUGH AUTHENTIC MATERIALS

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Annotation: This current study was intended to investigate the student point of views on the use of authentic materials (AMs) used in the process of teaching and learning speaking. To make the data display clear, the findings were classified into three classes; they were students' views on the use of videos, student' views on dialogues used in Basic Speaking, and students's point of views on the pictures used as Ams. In general, the interview results showed that AMs were basically interesting, motivating, providing information on how the language used and how English culture is, raising students' feeling of confidence.

Keywords: Basic speaking, students' view, authentic materials

INTRODUCTION

Being able to speak is the ultimate indication that ones have mastered a language; this does not only happen in learning first language but also in learning foreign language (FL). Unfortunately, speaking by using foreign language, English particularly, has been reported as a complex task for learners due to the fact that, to be able to deliver an effective communication, learners are supposed to use the language properly in social interaction. Further, Shumin adds that what makes speaking English as a foreign language complicated is that it does not involve linguistic elements as vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation only but also involves paralinguistic elements (pitch, stress, and intonation)¹.

¹ Al Azri, R.H, & Al-Rashdi, M.J. (2014). The Effect of Using Authentic Materials in Teaching. IJSTR (Vol3) No 10 Retrieved from www.ijstr.org/final_print/The-Effect-Of-Using...pdf on July 2016

Considering the complexity in speaking by using English as a foreign language (EFL), EFL teachers, therefore, do need to understand well how to facilitate their students to be able to communicate by using the target language. To enable the EFL teachers to facilitate learning, there are some principles teachers need to bear in mind when they intend to obtain such goals; amongst of them are understanding students' psychology, classroom managements, selecting suitable teaching strategies and media as well as teaching materials. Focusing on teaching speaking highlights that one of the principles EFL teachers need to hold in teaching speaking is putting up authentic language during the teaching. Therefore, to be able to provide authentic language, teachers need to give their students authentic materials.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Definition of Authentic Materials - The term authentic materials have been defined in different ways throughout the literature. Nunan states that authentic materials are not always produced for the purpose of language teaching. Little et al. declare that authentic materials are used for some social purposes in the language context where they are produced. Bacon and Finnemann also state that authentic materials are those texts which are made by native speakers for non-pedagogical purposes. This paper will assume Bacon and Finnemann's definition because their definition specifies the producers of the text as native speakers, whereas the others do not.

Discussing about authentic materials, some definitions have already been uttered by experts as Dascalos and Ling; they claim that authentic materials refer to language used in society's daily life and is not meant for pedagogical communication. Talking about non pedagogical communication in authentic material domain, Belaid and Murray put it as the appropriateness of the materials

with the students' need and the learning objectives². The two given definitions, lead us into an insight that, in language teaching field, authentic material is that any written and spoken language which the students hear, see, and use in their daily life; the language is not meant for educational purposes but still can be so beneficial in the teaching and learning language process. Some benefits of using authentic materials are they contribute a positive effect on student motivation; provide students information about the real culture of the target language; expose students to real language; relate more closely to students' needs; and support more creative approach to teaching. Further Harmer state that authentic materials have good impact on language learners because they can assist learners to produce better language output; help learners acquire the target language; and boost students' confidence to deal with language used in real life³.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study involved 22 students.

The results of interview about the student views on the use authentic materials were generally classified into six classes to specifically cover their views on the video, picture, and dialogue included to the developed Authentic Materials (AMs). The brief description of students' views on the video used in Authentic Materials (AMs) is displayed in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Brief Description of Students Views on the videos used as Authentic Materials (AMs)

No	Students' Views	Number of students	Percentage (%)
1	Interesting	21	95.5
2	Motivating	18	81.8

² Aqib, Zainal. (2013). *Model-Model Media dan Strategi Pembelajaran Kontekstual (Inovatif)*. Bandung: Yrama Widya.

³ Belaid, A.M, Murray, L. (2015). *Using Authentic Materials in the Foreign Language Classroom: Teacher Attitudes and Perception in Libyan University*. International Journal of Learning and Development (5) No 3. Online. Retrieved on July 14th from www.macrothink.org/ijld

3	Providing information how English cultures are	22	100
4	Providing information how to use the language	18	81.8
5	Raising student confidence	15	68
6	Understandable	9	40.9

From Table 1, we can see that in general, authentic materials (AMs), especially in term of materials presented in videos, were viewed positively by the EFL students at *Basic Speaking* class. This was so because 21 students admitted that authentic materials were interesting because they were so excited to watch how native speakers of English spoke. Next reason why the subjects of the study claimed to have positive attitude toward the use of videos because 18 students admitted that those videos were motivating; after watching video during the teaching of speaking, some students said that they wanted to learn English in order to be able travel around the world. Furthermore, 68% or 15 students stated that the AMs presented in the videos could boost their confidence. Dealing with raising student confidence, some students confessed that after watching video, in which the speakers made pauses and incomplete sentence, they found that it was fine to make flaws in speaking. The students' statement indicated that well structured dialogues, which we mostly find in speaking materials, could sometimes discourage the students to perform oral communication. By presenting AMs, particularly in forms of videos, to the students, teachers simultaneously have demonstrated that oral communication does not always need to run flawlessly. Even though students showed their positive views on the implementation of AMs, a question related to the comprehensible language got negative response as only 9 out of 22 admitted that they could understand the spoken discourse used in the videos; the others said that it was hard to catch the words pronounced by the native speakers. This situation is quite

understandable for the students' real environment those spoken discourses were hard to be found. If it happened to be easy to find those spoken communications from the internet, students still found difficulties to imitate linguistic and paralinguistic elements such as intonation, pitch, and stress. This happened due to the fact that, in EFL students' real life, students only could practice their English and get corrective feedback when they were in campus; and this sometimes hindered the students from interacting and speaking by using the target language.

CONCLUSION

The above findings and discussion lead us into conclusion that the implementation of authentic materials in *Basic Speaking* class were responded positively by the EFL learners⁴. This conclusion was made because from the interview, students agreed with the existing ideas about the benefits of AMs declared by some scholars. Focusing on the implementation of authentic materials, EFL teachers do need to consider the complexity degrees of the AMs so that the AMs will be comprehended easily by the EFL learners.

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⁴ Brown, H.D. (2007). *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. New York: Pearson Education

4. Brown, H.D. (2007). *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. New York: Pearson Education
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